

ANNEXURE 1A

Solution to the confined aquifer conceptual model

The governing differential equation of groundwater flow in a confined aquifer is given by

$$\frac{\partial^2 h_f}{\partial x^2} = \frac{S_s}{k} \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Where S_s is specific storage and k is hydraulic conductivity of the soil.

Taking $\mu = \frac{S_s}{k}$ Eq. (1) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial^2 h_f}{\partial x^2} = \mu \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

Now as $h_f = \frac{z}{\gamma}$, Eq. (2) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \frac{z}{\gamma}}{\partial x^2} = \mu \frac{\partial \frac{z}{\gamma}}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

γ can be written as following

$$\gamma = \frac{\rho_f}{\rho_s - \rho_f} \quad (4)$$

where, $\gamma \approx 40$

Now using Eq. (4) in the Eq. (3)

$$\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} = \mu \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \quad (5)$$

The initial and boundary conditions for Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) and (8) are given as

$$@ t = 0, \quad \text{for } z \leq 0, \quad z^2 = \begin{cases} \frac{H_L^2}{x_t}, & x \leq x_t \\ H_L^2, & x \geq x_t \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$@ x = 0, \quad z = \alpha t \quad (7)$$

Here α is the rate at which the sea-level rises at the coast due to climate change.

$$@ x = L, \quad z = -H_L \quad (8)$$

To solve Eq. (5) with initial condition and boundary conditions mentioned in Eq. (6), (7) and (8), Let us take a variable $v(x, t)$ such that $v(0, t)$ and $v(L, t)$ vanishes i.e., $v(0, t) = v(L, t) = 0$.

$$v(x, t) = z(x, t) + Ax + B \quad \dots (9)$$

Where $Ax + B$ will take care of steady state solution and $v(x, t)$ will take care of transient part solutions. Now put $v(0, t) = v(L, t) = 0$ in the Eq. (9) will give $A = \frac{H_L + \alpha t}{L}$ and $B = -\alpha t$ Now the Eq. (9) is changed to the following form after putting A and B in the equation

$$v(x, t) = z(x, t) + \frac{H_L + \alpha t}{L} x - \alpha t \quad (10)$$

Now differentiate the Eq. (10) to get the value of $\frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2}$ and $\frac{\partial z}{\partial t}$

$$\text{So } \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} \text{ and } \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \alpha \left[1 - \frac{x}{L}\right] \quad (11)$$

Now satisfy the initial condition given for the Eq. (6) in the equation (10)

$$v(x, 0) = z(x, 0) + \frac{H_L + \alpha \times 0}{L} x - \alpha \times 0 \quad (12)$$

$v(x, 0)$

$$= \begin{cases} H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \right] & \text{if } x \leq x_t \\ H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - 1 \right] & \text{if } x \geq x_t \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

So now if we put the Eq. (11) values in the Eq. (6) then we will get the following non-homogeneous equation with homogeneous boundary condition;

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} = \mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \mu \alpha \left\{1 - \frac{x}{L}\right\} = \mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + F(x, t) \text{ where } F(x, t) = \mu \alpha \left\{1 - \frac{x}{L}\right\} \quad (14)$$

With Boundary Conditions

$$v(0, t) = v(L, t) = 0 \quad (14(a))$$

Initial Condition

$$v(x, 0) = \begin{cases} H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \right] & \text{if } x \leq x_t \\ H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - 1 \right] & \text{if } x \geq x_t \end{cases} \quad (14(b))$$

Now the solution of Eq. (14) is found by the superposition of the two solutions;

(A) One with $F(x, t) = 0$ subjected to condition 14(a) and 14(b).

(B) One with $F(x, t) \neq 0$ subjected to zero initial condition.

Now for solution of the part (A) we have $F(x, t) = 0$ so

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} = \mu \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} \tag{15}$$

We will use separation of variable method. Let's take

$$v(x,t)=X(x)T(t)$$

So, after differentiating the above equation with respect to x and t we will get

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} = v''(x, t) = X''(x)T(t) \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = v'(x, t) = X(x)T'(t) \tag{16}$$

Substituting equation (16) in equation (15) we get

$$X''(x)T(t) = \mu X(x)T'(t)$$

$$\frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} = \mu \frac{T'(t)}{T(t)} = k(\text{say}) \tag{17}$$

Now we will solve equation (17) for different value of k.

Now take $\frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} = k$

Condition 1: Let's take $k = 0$

So
$$\frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} = 0 \Rightarrow X''(x) = 0 \Rightarrow X(x) = Ax + B \tag{18}$$

NOTE: - $v(x,t)=X(x)T(t)$

$$v(0, t)=X(0)T(t)=0 \dots \dots \dots (c)$$

$$v(L,t)=X(L)T(t)=0 \dots \dots \dots (d)$$

The equation 14(a) and 14(b) shows that $X(0)$ and $X(L)$ should be zero. $T(t)$ cannot be zero.

In equation (18) if we keep $X(0) = X(L)=0$ then the coefficient A and B will be zero and it will lead to trivial solution which is of no interest.

Condition 2: Let us take $k = \sigma^2$ where σ is positive number.

So

$$X''(x) - \sigma^2 X(x) = 0 \Rightarrow X(x) = Ae^{\sigma x} + Be^{-\sigma x}$$

$$X(0) = A + B = 0 \text{ and } X(L) = Ae^{\sigma L} + Be^{-\sigma L} = 0 \quad (19)$$

So, equation (19) will again give $A = 0$ and $B = 0$ and it will lead to trivial solution in which we are not interested.

Condition 3: Let's take $k = -\sigma^2$

So,

$$X''(x) + \sigma^2 X(x) = 0 \Rightarrow X(x) = A\cos\sigma x + B\sin\sigma x$$

$$\text{Now } X(0) = A\cos(\sigma \times 0) + B\sin(\sigma \times 0) = 0$$

$$\text{i. e. } A = 0$$

$$\text{Also, } X(L) = A\cos(\sigma \times L) + B\sin(\sigma \times L) = 0 \Rightarrow B\sin(\sigma \times L) = 0$$

Here B cannot be zero otherwise we will get trivial solution again. So, the only thing is that

$$\sin(\sigma \times L) = 0 \Rightarrow \sigma = \frac{n\pi}{L}, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Where, σ is the Eigen value of the solution.

So,

$$X_n(x) = B_n \sin(\sigma_n x) = B_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x\right) \quad (20)$$

Now taking the time varying part from equation (17), so

$$\mu \frac{T'(t)}{T(t)} = k = -\sigma^2 \Rightarrow \frac{T'(t)}{T(t)} = \frac{-\sigma^2}{\mu} = -\beta^2 \text{ where, } \frac{\sigma^2}{\mu} = \beta^2 \Rightarrow \frac{T'(t)}{T(t)} = -\beta^2$$

$$\frac{dT(t)}{T(t)} = -\beta^2 dt \quad \Rightarrow \quad T_n(t) = C_n e^{-\beta_n^2 t} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{So, } v_n(x, t) = X_n(x)T_n(t) = \overline{C}_n \sin(\sigma_n x) e^{-\beta_n^2 t}, \text{ where } \overline{C}_n = C_n B_n$$

Hence,

$$v(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_n(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{C}_n \sin(\sigma_n x) e^{-\beta_n^2 t} \quad (22)$$

Now, inserting the initial condition given in equation 14(b) in the equation (22) we get

$$v(x, 0) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \overline{C}_n \sin(\sigma_n x) = \begin{cases} H_L \left[\frac{x}{l} - \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \right], & x \leq x_t \\ H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - 1 \right], & x \geq x_t \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

The coefficient \overline{C}_n can be obtained by

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{C}_n &= \frac{2}{L} \left[\int_0^{x_t} H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \right] \sin(\sigma_n x) dx + \int_{x_t}^L H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - 1 \right] \sin(\sigma_n x) dx \right] \\ \overline{C}_n &= \frac{2H_L}{L} \left[\int_0^{x_t} \frac{x}{L} \sin(\sigma_n x) dx - \int_0^{x_t} \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \sin \left(\frac{n\pi x}{L} \right) dx + \int_{x_t}^L H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - 1 \right] \sin(\sigma_n x) dx \right] \quad (24)\end{aligned}$$

$$\overline{C}_n = \frac{2H_L}{L} [I_1 - I_2 + I_3] \quad \text{Where,}$$

$$I_1 = \int_0^{x_t} \frac{x}{L} \sin(\sigma_n x) dx, \quad I = \int_0^{x_t} \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \sin \left(\frac{n\pi x}{L} \right) dx, \quad I_3 = \int_{x_t}^L H_L \left[\frac{x}{L} - 1 \right] \sin(\sigma_n x) dx$$

Here the integration of I_1 and I_3 can be done analytically but the integration of part I is analytically not possible. So, for solving I_2 we can go for numerical method. So, after doing the analytical integration for I_1 and I_3 the Fourier coefficient \overline{C}_n can be written in the following form

$$\overline{C}_n = \frac{2H_L}{L} \left[-\frac{L}{n\pi} \cos \left(\frac{n\pi x_t}{L} \right) - \int_0^{x_t} \sqrt{\frac{x}{x_t}} \sin \left(\frac{n\pi x}{L} \right) dx \right] \quad (25)$$

So, the complete solution for part A will be

$$v_I(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_n(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2H_L}{L} \left[-I - \frac{L}{n\pi} \cos \left(\frac{n\pi x_t}{L} \right) \right] \sin \left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x \right) e^{\left(\frac{-n^2 \pi^2}{L^2 \mu} t \right)} \quad (26)$$

Now to get the solution for the part B, each term $v(x, t)$ and $F(x, t)$ present in the Eq. (14) is expanded in the form of Fourier sine series considered as function of x over $[0, L]$ in the form

$$v_{II}(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_n(t) \sin(\sigma_n x) \quad \text{and} \quad F(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n(t) \sin(\sigma_n x) \quad (27)$$

Where $v_n(t)$ and $F_n(t)$ are the Fourier coefficient in half range sine series and given by the following equations

$$v_n(t) = \frac{2}{L} \int_0^L v(\omega, t) \sin(\sigma_n \omega) d\omega \quad \text{and} \quad F_n(t) = \frac{2}{L} \int_0^L F(\omega, t) \sin(\sigma_n \omega) d\omega \quad (28)$$

Now keep the value of Eq. (27) in the Eq. (14) so it will give,

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_n(t) \sigma_n^2 \sin(\sigma_n x) = \mu' \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \dot{v}_n(t) \sin(\sigma_n x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n(t) \sin(\sigma_n x) \quad (29)$$

Now comparing the both side and taking the coefficient of $\sin(\sigma_n x)$ in Eq. (29)

$$-v_n(t) \sigma_n^2 = \mu \dot{v}_n(t) + F_n(t) \quad \text{or} \quad \dot{v}_n(t) + \frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} v_n(t) = \frac{-F_n(t)}{\mu} \quad (30)$$

Eq. (30) given is the linear first order differential equation and can be solved for $v_n(t)$. So, integrating factor (I.F.) for the solution is

$$\text{I. F.} = e^{\int \frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} dt} = e^{\frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t}$$

So, the solution of the Eq. (30) is

$$v_n(t) \times (\text{I. F.}) = \int_0^t \frac{-F_n(t)}{\mu} \times (\text{I. F.}) dt \quad (31)$$

Where $F_n(t)$ can be calculated as

$$F_n(t) = \frac{2}{L} \int_0^L \mu \alpha \left(1 - \frac{x}{L}\right) \sin(\sigma_n x) dx = \frac{2\mu\alpha}{n\pi}$$

Put $F_n(t)$ in the Eq. (31) so we have

$$v_n(t) \times \left(e^{\frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t}\right) = \int_0^t \frac{-2\alpha}{n\pi} \times \left(e^{\frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t}\right) dt \Rightarrow v_n(t) \times \left(e^{\frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t}\right) = \frac{-2\alpha}{n\pi} \left[\frac{e^{\frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t}}{\frac{\sigma_n^2}{\mu}} \right]_0^t$$

$$v_n(t) = \frac{2\alpha\mu L^2}{n^3\pi^3} \left[e^{\frac{-\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t} - 1 \right]$$

Put $v_n(t)$ value in the Eq. (27) we will get the solution for the part B as

$$v_{II}(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} v_n(t) \sin(\sigma_n x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\alpha\mu L^2}{n^3\pi^3} \left[e^{\frac{-\sigma_n^2}{\mu} t} - 1 \right] \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x\right) \quad (32)$$

So, the solution of the Eq. (14) subjected to condition 14(a) and 14(b) is the superposition of solution of part A and part B i.e., sum of the Eq. (26) and Eq. (32) as,

$$v(x, t) = v_I(x, t) + v_{II}(x, t)$$

$$v(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2HL}{L} \left[-I - \frac{L}{n\pi} \cos\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right) \right] \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x\right) e^{\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2}{L^2\mu} t\right)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\alpha\mu L^2}{n^3\pi^3} \left[e^{\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2}{L^2\mu} t\right)} - 1 \right] \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x\right) \quad (33)$$

So, the final solution for $z(x, t)$ can be obtained by putting $v(x, t)$ from Eq. (33) to equation (10). So, from Eq. (10)

$$z(x, t) = v(x, t) - \frac{H_L + \alpha t}{L} x + \alpha t$$

$$z(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2H_L}{L} \left[-I - \frac{L}{n\pi} \cos\left(\frac{n\pi x_L}{L}\right) \right] \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x\right) e^{\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2}{L^2\mu} t\right)} \\ + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\alpha\mu L^2}{n^3\pi^3} \left[e^{\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2}{L^2\mu} t\right)} - 1 \right] \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x\right) - \frac{H_L + \alpha t}{L} x + \alpha t \quad (34)$$

Equation (34) is the analytical solution for sea water intrusion in coastal confined aquifer.

ANNEXURE 1B

Solution to the unconfined aquifer conceptual model

The governing differential equation of groundwater flow in an unconfined aquifer, given by Boussinesq's equation with Dupuit's assumptions, is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[h \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial x} \right] = \frac{S_{ya}}{k} \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Where, S_{ya} is specific yield of aquifer. Replacing head h by $(h_f + z)$ gives

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(h_f + z) \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial x} \right] = \frac{S_{ya}}{k} \frac{\partial h_f}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

We have assumed that *here* $h_f = h_f(x, t)$. So, applying the Ghyben-Herzberg relation for seawater-freshwater sharp SFI and considering $h_f = \frac{z}{\alpha}$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left(\frac{z}{\gamma} + z \right) \frac{\partial \frac{z}{\gamma}}{\partial x} \right] = \frac{S_{ya}}{k} \frac{\partial \frac{z}{\gamma}}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\gamma} + 1 \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[z \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right] = \frac{S_{ya}}{k} \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \Rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(z \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{S_{ya}}{k \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} + 1 \right)} \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(z \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right) = \mu \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \quad \text{where} \quad \frac{S_{ya}}{k \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} + 1 \right)} = \mu \quad (5)$$

The initial and boundary conditions for Eq. (5) are

$$@ t = 0, \quad z = -H_s + H_s \exp(-\beta x) \quad (6)$$

where, β is a constant taken to adjust the initial length of intrusion

$$@ x = 0, \quad z = at \quad (7)$$

$$@ x = L, \quad z = -H_s \quad (8)$$

Eq. (5) is a nonlinear second-order partial differential equation and is solved semi-analytically by the Perturbation method. The approximate analytical solution of the Eq. (5) can be obtained by the perturbation method. For this we are introducing the new non-dimensional variables ([Ketabchi et al. 2013](#)) in the Eq. (5)

$$X = \frac{x}{L}, \quad H = \frac{H_s - z}{D - H_s}, \quad T = \frac{t}{\mu L} \quad (9)$$

Now converting all terms in Eq. (5) in the non-dimensional form. For this

$$\mu \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} = \mu \frac{\partial z}{\partial T} \times \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \mu \frac{\partial [H_s - H(D - H_s)]}{\partial T} \frac{1}{\mu L} \Rightarrow \mu \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} = \frac{-(D - H_s)}{L} \frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \quad (10)$$

$$\mu \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} = -\varepsilon \frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \quad \text{where} \quad \frac{(D - H_s)}{L} = \varepsilon \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial[H_s - H(D - H_s)]}{\partial X} \times \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} = -(D - H_s) \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} \times \frac{1}{L} = -\varepsilon \frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \quad (12)$$

Hence

$$z \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} = -\varepsilon z \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} = -\varepsilon[H_s - H(D - H_s)] \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} = -\varepsilon H_s \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} + \varepsilon(D - H_s)H \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(z \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} \right) = -\frac{1}{L} \varepsilon H_s \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial X^2} + \varepsilon^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} \right) \quad (14)$$

Now substituting Eq. (11) and Eq. (14) in the Eq. (5) we have

$$-\frac{\partial H}{\partial T} = -\frac{1}{L} H_s \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial X^2} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} \right) \quad (15)$$

Let the solution of the above Eq. (15) is

$$H = H_0 + \varepsilon H_1 + \varepsilon^2 H_2 + \dots \quad (16)$$

So, Eq. (16) should satisfy Eq. (15). It will give

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{\partial H_0}{\partial T} - \varepsilon \frac{\partial H_1}{\partial T} &= \frac{-H_s \partial^2 H_0}{L \partial X^2} - \frac{\varepsilon H_s \partial^2 H_1}{L \partial X^2} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left\{ (H_0 + \varepsilon H_1) \left(\frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial H_1}{\partial X} \right) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-H_s \partial^2 H_0}{L \partial X^2} + \varepsilon \left\{ \frac{-H_s \partial^2 H_1}{L \partial X^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_0 \frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} \right) \right\} + \varepsilon^2 \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_0 \frac{\partial H_1}{\partial X} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_1 \frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} \right) \right\} \\ &+ \varepsilon^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_1 \frac{\partial H_1}{\partial X} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Now in Eq. (18), comparing the coefficients of ε^0 in both side

$$\frac{\partial H_0}{\partial T} = \frac{H_s \partial^2 H_0}{L \partial X^2} \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) is subjected to the following non-dimensional initial and boundary conditions.

$$@ x = 0, \quad z = \alpha t \Rightarrow XL = 0, \quad z = \alpha T \mu L \Rightarrow X = 0, \quad H_0 = \frac{H_s - \alpha T \mu L}{D - H_s} \quad (20)$$

$$@ x = L, \quad z = -H_s \Rightarrow XL = L, \quad z = -H_s \Rightarrow X = 1, \quad H_0 = \frac{2H_s}{D - H_s} \quad (21)$$

$$@ t = 0, z = -H_s + H_s \exp(-\beta x) \Rightarrow T \mu L = 0, \quad z = -H_s + H_s \exp(-\beta XL) \quad (22)$$

$$\Rightarrow T = 0, \quad H_0 = \frac{2H_s - H_s \exp(-\beta XL)}{D - H_s} \quad (23)$$

Eq. (19) subjected to the above initial condition is solved using the separation of variable method as discussed in ANNEXURE 1A.

$$\begin{aligned}
& H_0(X, T) \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n \sin(n\pi X) \exp\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\mu^2 L^2 \alpha}{n^3 \pi^3 (D - H_s)} \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right)\right] \sin(n\pi X) \\
&+ \left(\frac{H_s}{D - H_s} + \frac{\alpha T \mu L}{D - H_s}\right) \\
&+ \frac{H_s - \alpha T \mu L}{D - H_s} \tag{24}
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$C_n = \frac{H_s}{D - H_s} \times \left[\frac{1}{n\pi} - \frac{1 - (-1)^n \exp(-\beta L)}{n\pi + \beta^2 L^2 / (n\pi)} \right] \tag{25}$$

Again, comparing the coefficient of ε^1 in Eq. (18) we will get

$$\frac{\partial H_1}{\partial T} = \frac{H_s}{L} \frac{\partial^2 H_1}{\partial X^2} - \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_0 \frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} \right) \tag{26}$$

Here we are taking the both initial and boundary condition zero because we have already considered the initial and boundary condition in Eq. (19). Now the initial condition is:

$$H_1(X, 0) = 0 \tag{27}$$

Similarly, the boundary conditions

$$H_1(0, T) = H_1(1, T) = 0 \tag{28}$$

Solution for Eq. (26) can be found using separation of variable method

$$\begin{aligned}
& H_1(X, T) \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-2}{\exp\left(\frac{n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right)} \int_0^T \left\{ \int_0^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_0 \frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} \right) \sin(n\pi X) dX \right\} \exp\left(\frac{n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right) dT \right] \sin(n\pi X) \tag{29}
\end{aligned}$$

Replacing Eq. (24) and Eq. (29) in Eq. (16), we will get

$$\begin{aligned}
& H \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n \sin(n\pi X) \exp\left(\frac{-n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\mu^2 L^2 \alpha}{n^3 \pi^3 (D - H_s)} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}}\right] \sin(n\pi X) \\
&+ \left(\frac{H_s}{D - H_s} + \frac{\alpha T \mu L}{D - H_s}\right) X + \frac{H_s - \alpha T \mu L}{D - H_s} \\
&+ \varepsilon \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-2}{\exp\left(\frac{n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right)} \int_0^T \left\{ \int_0^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_0 \frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} \right) \sin(n\pi X) dX \right\} \exp\left(\frac{n^2\pi^2 T}{\mu}\right) dT \right] \sin(n\pi X) \tag{30}
\end{aligned}$$

Now replacing the value of $H = \frac{H_s - z}{D - H_s}$, $X = \frac{x}{L}$ and $T = \frac{t}{\mu L}$ $\varepsilon = \frac{(D - H_s)}{L}$ in the Eq. (30) will give

z

$$\begin{aligned}
&= (H_s - D) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{l}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-n^2 \pi^2 t}{\mu^2 L}\right) \\
&- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2\mu^2 L^2 \alpha}{n^3 \pi^3} \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{-n^2 \pi^2 t}{\mu^2 L}\right)\right] \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{L}\right) - (H_s + \alpha t) \frac{x}{L} + \alpha t \\
&- \frac{(D - H_s)^2}{L} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-2}{\exp\left(\frac{n^2 \pi^2 T}{\mu}\right)} \int_0^T \left\{ \int_0^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(H_0 \frac{\partial H_0}{\partial X} \right) \sin(n\pi X) dX \right\} \exp\left(\frac{n^2 \pi^2 T}{\mu}\right) dT \right] \sin(n\pi X) \dots (31)
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. (31) presents the closed-form solution for the transient movement of the sharp SFI into a coastal unconfined aquifer, due to SLR.

ANNEXURE 1C

Fig. S1. Locations of the coastal aquifers from the east and west coasts of India.

References

Ketabchi, H., Mahmoodzadeh, D., Ataie-Ashtiani, B., Werner, A. D., & Simmons, C. T. 2013. "Sea-level rise impact on fresh groundwater lenses in two-layer small islands." *Hydrological Processes*, 28(24), 5938–5953. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10059>.